

Interview with Javier García, Spanish Artist at Capcom

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Good morning, readers. On this occasion, we present the interview conducted by our team with Javier García Oliva, a professional Spanish artist and video game enthusiast, whose dream was to work in the industry—a goal he successfully achieved. He has worked for, among others, the eminent company Capcom, responsible for legendary franchises such as Resident Evil, Street Fighter, and Megaman (Rockman), in its Vancouver division, Canada. Javier has contributed to franchises such as Puzzle Fighter and Dead Rising, and you can view some of his works on his personal website and Pinterest profile.

Interview with Javier García Oliva

Cool Japan: Can you tell us about your career, Javier?

Javier García: My career in the video game industry is not very long; I've been working at Capcom Vancouver for nearly two years. Before that, I spent seven years working as a graphic designer and illustrator for various companies. I have always been passionate about art, and it's something I love and wouldn't change for anything.

CJ: Have you always been interested in working in video games?

JG: Yes, video games have always been part of my life, and I still enjoy them every day. When I began my studies, there wasn't an option to study video games in Spain, so I started with Fine Arts and Graphic Design. Still, I experimented early with RPG Maker and M.U.G.E.N., and away from the keyboard, I often created board games, which are also fundamental when it comes to developing electronic entertainment.

CJ: What was your first job in the industry?

JG: When I joined Capcom Vancouver, they were about to announce *Dead Rising 4* at E3 Los Angeles, so I joined the team to work on the trailer that was shown. Due to my experience in graphic design and multimedia, I was given many tasks related to video and marketing. Within the game itself, my first assignments were creating tutorials, capturing assets, and tidying up some menus—UI, user interface—to make them visually more attractive. By the end of the project, I ended up modelling some weapons and objects as well; I believe it was a total of eight.

Javier García and Sonic wished us a Merry Christmas from the Capcom Vancouver offices during the 2017–2018 holiday season.

CJ: You currently work for the prestigious company Capcom, one of the most veteran in the history of video games. How does it feel working for them? How did you get the job?

JG: I can't think of anything negative about Capcom Vancouver. What stands out to me is the effort they put into keeping their employees happy. I believe a happy worker reflects in the quality of the product. They incentivise us with gifts and group activities—they take us to amusement parks, picnics, invite us to meals, give us company merchandise and games, we have hockey, football, baseball teams... even clubs, like astronomy or virtual reality, just to name a few.

Capcom has always been one of my favourite companies, probably the one that has given me the most hours of entertainment. So, when I graduated from the video game course, it was my first choice. I sent them my résumé and portfolio for a development support position, and they offered me a job, which I gladly accepted. In less than a year, they offered me an artist position.

CJ: What do you enjoy most about your work? It seems you handle both 3D and 2D art. Which do you feel more comfortable with?

JG: What I enjoy most is learning. As I mentioned, I haven't been in this field for long, but I work alongside people with 10 or even 20 years of experience making games. Learning from them is an incredible opportunity to absorb new knowledge and apply it. Regarding 2D vs 3D, for comfort, I feel more at ease with 2D, as I have many years of experience in this format. 3D, on the other hand, is a world I entered only three years ago, but now I use it daily and enjoy it like a child with a new toy. To put it simply, it's like saying my "favourite game" is 2D, but the one I play lately is 3D.

CJ: What is the hardest part of working in the video game industry for you? What advice would you give to people considering a career in this sector?

JG: The hardest part is probably the days leading up to a release. Before a game sees the light of day, it must be sent for certification—PEGI, ESRB, ZERO...—and to the company responsible for the platform, to meet quality standards. In the case of *Dead Rising 4*, it was Microsoft for Xbox One and Steam/Valve for PC, and later Sony for PS4. These deadlines are immovable and create a lot of stress, since so much company money is at stake. People often work long hours, even weeks, before these deadlines.

My advice for anyone wanting to pursue this career is dedication, effort, and patience. Nowadays, it's much easier to learn independently online. Spend time, share your work, get feedback, take notes, and iterate. Attending a school is also valuable for networking, which can sometimes be even more important than the curriculum itself. We live in a very competitive world, so setting aside shyness is crucial. Talk to people, ask questions, show interest, make friendships—who knows, a classmate could recommend you to their company in a couple of years.

CJ: What qualities are necessary to work in video game design, based on your professional experience?

JG: If you lack experience, you can always start as a QA tester. It's a very good entry point for other roles in the industry. More generally, I'd say persistence, hard work, and passion for games. Having an open and critical mind also helps a lot. Playing all types of games—even genres you don't usually enjoy—develops creativity and teaches lessons you wouldn't notice playing only your favourites.

CJ: Recently, you worked on the new *Puzzle Fighter* for Capcom, a spin-off featuring characters from various company franchises. What challenge did the art team face in creating a visual style that suited all these characters?

JG: It's true that I contributed to *Puzzle Fighter*, but my work was limited to marketing and video editing—trailers and promos—so I can't fully answer that question. I can assure you, though, that the art team worked very hard to create a consistent style that satisfied both Western and Asian markets, keeping an “Americanised” look—after all, we're in North America—but without losing the Japanese identity of these characters.

CJ: What influences your work most? Do you draw inspiration from other visual artists, or does music help you create?

JG: Seeing other people's work always influences my style. I seek inspiration from different visual styles, never sticking to a single one, and I try to incorporate a bit of everything I've learned. Although I've always leaned towards anime and manga, you can learn from Disney, visiting classical art museums, reading Marvel comics, or exploring other artists' websites and social media. You never—repeat, never—stop learning.

Regarding music, I listen to everything, and it accompanies me daily. Some days, for example, I might play Linkin Park at full volume, while on others I listen to orchestral music, like the *Shenmue* soundtrack. Music helps me focus and develop my work.

Javier García working on a three-dimensional model at the Capcom Vancouver offices.

CJ: The video game industry has many highly regarded artists. Do you have a favourite?

JG: Actually, yes. If I had to choose one, I would say Kinu Nishimura, an illustrator who has worked for Capcom for many years. I think that, alongside Akiman (Akira Yasuda), she represents the pinnacle of Capcom’s visual identity.

Outside the company, I would like to highlight Yōji Shinkawa, whom I was fortunate to meet a few years ago. He is responsible for the art of *Metal Gear*, from its PSX version onwards. His striking personal style is unmistakable and synonymous with the franchise.

CJ: Are you an artist who prefers digital, traditional, or a bit of both? Which tools and programs do you usually use?

JG: A bit of both. At work, I use 99.9% digital tools—I work with a Cintiq tablet, two additional screens, Maya, ZBrush, and Substance Painter. At home, I enjoy sketching on paper with pencil, painting with watercolours, or even making illustrations with coloured cards. Lately, I’ve been using alcohol-based markers a lot. In that sense, I’d say I’m quite versatile.

CJ: Can you tell us how a video game studio operates? How many people do you usually work with? What can you tell us about your workflow in a studio?

JG: Capcom Vancouver is a studio with around 300 employees, but it’s divided into teams based on projects. In my case, my team has about 30 people, as we are in the pre-production phase of a new title. When we reach “full production,” there will be over 100 of us.

Regarding how it operates, there’s a chain of command, like in many other companies, but our opinions are always considered, listened to, and reviewed. There’s no issue with approaching the studio director directly—their door is always open.

As for my workflow nowadays, I can summarise it like this: I receive designs for an object from the concept artist, which have already been approved by the art director. I sculpt a low-resolution model (low poly) in Maya, unwrap the UVs [this refers to texture mapping on the model], and then create the same model in higher detail and polygon count (high poly) in Maya or ZBrush. I transfer (bake) the maps from the hi-poly model to the low-poly in Substance Painter and paint textures and materials. Then I add my model and its textures into the engine—in the case of the current project, Unreal Engine 4—and place it in the corresponding level, or hand it to the environment artist if they’re responsible for “dressing” the levels.

CJ: Can you tell us about your upcoming projects? Are you currently working on any titles for Capcom?

JG: Honestly, not much [laughs]. Capcom Vancouver is currently handling the maintenance of *Dead Rising 4*, updates for *Puzzle Fighter*, and a couple of other projects I can't talk about if I want to keep working here when this interview is published.

I'm involved in one of those two.

Javier García, with artwork of Megaman and Ryū from Street Fighter... Hadōken!!

Acknowledgements

We thank Javier García Oliva for his time and kindness in granting this interview. From CoolJapan.es, we wish him continued success in pursuing his dream and congratulate him on his work. We are very proud that professionals from our country, like Javier García, contribute their talents to such prestigious companies, crucial to both the Japanese and international video game industry, such as Capcom —and this is not the only major company in which he has worked. We also extend our gratitude to our colleague Juan Carlos Pérez, without whom this interview could not have taken place.

Sources

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